

Revive The Youth and Freshness of The Ovary with The PRP Injection Technique

Sura A. Awadh¹, Rawaa S. A. AL-Azawi², Karar Salih Mahdi³,
Shaimaa A. Al-Oubaidy⁴

^{1,2}Biology Department, College of Science, Al-Qasim Green University, Babylon, 51013, Iraq

³Pathological analysis department, College of Science, Al-Qasim Green University, Babylon, 51013, Iraq

⁴Anatomy department, College of Medicine, University of Babylon

Ovarian rejuvenation and endometrial therapy by Platelet Rich Plasma (PRP) injection

It is considered a modern method, although research and experiments began more than ten years ago, beginning with joint and muscle injections, and expanded to other fields, including neurology, plastic surgery, and many others until it began to be used recently in the uterus and ovaries (1).

In our contemporary world, the age of childbearing is increasing for many social and cultural reasons, and with age, the number and quality of eggs decreases, and thus the chance of pregnancy decreases and the risk of miscarriage increases. In this case, the chance of pregnancy decreases even with advanced advanced treatments such as artificial insemination techniques (2,3). For this reason, new scientific attempts and experiments have begun to regenerate ovarian tissue recently, with the aim of obtaining better quality eggs and achieving successful results at advanced ages.

PRP (Platelet Rich Plasma Injection) technique is the use of a natural blood product that contains platelets and high concentration growth factors derived from the patient's own blood (4,5). These factors play an important role in cell regeneration, recovery from inactivity, and tissue regeneration and angiogenesis (6). Therefore, this technique is use to increase the ovarian reserve.

In order to implement the PRP technique, 150 ml of blood is first drawn from the patient and PRP is prepared in the laboratory, then under general anesthesia this fluid is injected into the patient's ovaries under ultrasound or laparoscopy Then, signs of ovarian regeneration can be looked for by looking at the levels of Anti-Mullerian Hormone (AMH), Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) and Estradiol (E2), monthly follow up (7,8). If the AMH rate rises and the FSH and E2 levels decrease, then this indicates the benefit of the PRP technique (9,10).

Because this process started a short time ago in various parts of the world, there is still not a lot of data and adequate statistical indications about the successes of this process (11). Studies have shown the formation of stem cells in the ovaries. It is believed that growth factors within the PRP technique (Platelet Rich Plasma injection) have an opportunity to activate these stem cells, and there are published reports claiming pregnancy with this technique in women who have not previously menstruated (12). As a result, ovarian regeneration with technology may be an option for patients who have a low chance of success with depletion of oocyte reserve or with advanced age who have tried several times before but failed to mature eggs (13).

In IVF, PRP can be applied to the uterus and ovaries. For patients with endometrial thickening or intrauterine adhesions due to previous procedures that caused damage, additional PRP therapy has been shown to contribute to thickening and regeneration of the endometrium (14).

The decrease in the quality of eggs as well as the decrease in the egg stock that appears in women due to advanced age or other reasons (previous surgery, endometriosis, radiotherapy - chemotherapy, etc.) are among the most important factors that affect the success of IVF treatment (15). There are many scientific articles showing that PRP therapy may have a therapeutic effect in women with low egg reserves (10).

Recent studies have shown that even in postmenopausal women, there may still be egg-producing stem cells inside the ovaries. The researchers presented serious results obtained from these cells indicating that they can re-experience egg production under the right conditions (16)

Platelet Rich Plasma technology in itself is not a stem cell therapy, but with its content it aims to ensure the regeneration of cells inside the ovary to produce egg cells (14). Oocyte production can be improved by

improving the conditions of the ovarian microenvironment, which are affected by age or other factors within the ovary, and the application of various growth factors to the ovary can help in this (17).

The injection process takes approximately 30-40 minutes, the patient is given a nutrient containing anesthetic substance conscious sedation for a short period, and after the injection, she remains under observation for an hour after which she goes out to practice her normal life. it becomes clear within the next 3-6 months (13).

As for the ovary, the response is that the ovary begins to produce eggs again, followed by ultrasound examination, the rise of estrogen and egg maturation, and a natural pregnancy may occur, or through artificial insemination or IVF, depending on the situation. As for the endometrium, its thickness increases by more than 6 mm, and the cycle returns to normal (3). This technique benefits from She suffers from a lack of ovarian reserve either due to age or the so-called early menopause, or she suffers from a weak endometrium less than 6 mm, either due to a previous surgical reason or inflammation and others (5).

Some cases may need stimulating hormones or a dose of plasma injections for the second or third time, and here it must be emphasized that there is 50 percent that may not benefit from this experience and there will be no response (17). Follow-up, especially in the early stages, is very important, especially that such new technologies do not It is still under study and needs more research to become in the future one of the treatment options for such difficult cases, in which the choice was more difficult. Either deprivation of offspring is the adornment of worldly life (7,16).

Plasma injection into the ovary

Recent evidence indicates that there are latent stem cells in the ovaries that can be activated and produce new eggs through plasma injection into the ovary to treat infertility and provide a greater chance of pregnancy (18). Ovarian plasma injection is an innovative treatment method that contributes to balancing the levels of hormones responsible for stimulating and renewing the ovaries to produce high-quality eggs. This technique relies on injecting plasma directly into the ovaries to reinforce the ovaries with proteins rich in growth and regeneration factors to increase the egg stock (19).

The growth factors present in PRP stem cells stimulate and activate stem cells in the ovaries to produce a quantity of healthy eggs.

Platelet-rich plasma treatment provides the opportunity to become pregnant for women in menopause for women who suffer from a lack of ovarian stock or from poor ovulation through the injection of concentrated plasma into the ovary. It is best to do injections of platelet-rich plasma during menstruation, before the formation of the egg follicle.

PRP into Endometrial cavity improves the endometrial receptivity by increasing the progesterone receptor activity resulting in healthy endometrium and successful pregnancy. Endometrial growth with PRP is a novel innovative effective and promising therapeutic method to improve its thickness and thereby the pregnancy rate. PRP injected in woman with poor ovarian reserve paved the way to successful ovarian rejuvenation within 1 - 3 months. PRP the newer field of rejuvenation medicine brings the Ray of Hope, for many unsolved problems in infertile couple (20).

The technique of activation and injection of plasma into the ovary includes two stages:

The first stage is preparation: Initially, 10-20 ml of blood is drawn intravenously and is processed. The platelet-rich plasma is separated from white blood cells and red blood cells by a procedure called centrifugation. The preparation of platelet-rich plasma takes less than one hour and platelet count should be 4-5 times the normal number (21).

The second stage is the injection into the ovaries: It involves giving the patient general anesthesia and then injecting the concentrated plasma into the ovary with a process called laparoscopy or through the ultrasound technique directed through the vagina. Plasma injection therapy may take 2-3 hours. Then levels of AMH, FSH, and estradiol (E2) are measure at monthly intervals for six months and a vaginal ultrasound is done to count the number of follicles inside the ovaries. If AMH levels rise, and FSH, LH, and estradiol levels decrease approximately 3 months after the ovarian plasma injection, this reflects the effectiveness of the plasma in improving ovarian function (22).

After the injection of plasma into the ovary: Ovarian plasma injection is a very safe procedure and it is normal for the patient to feel some cramping and discomfort for a short period and it usually goes away using pain relievers. The patient can go home on the same day. It is a completely safe technique for the uterus (23). There is no risk of blood-borne viral infection as the patient is injected with only her own platelet-rich plasma. The effectiveness of plasma is to improve ovarian function and thus reduce menopausal symptoms, return of the interrupted menstrual cycle and improve the quality of eggs and the effects of plasma last for a period ranging from 5 to 7 months (24).

Candidates for ovarian regeneration using rich plasma

- Women in early menopause or perimenopause.
- Delayed pregnancy in women due to poor ovulation.
- A female over 35 years old who has low ovarian reserve and low AMH levels.
- Women under the age of 35 who have a low egg reserve and low levels of anti-mullerian hormone.
- Women with premature ovarian failure (25)

Factors that contribute to the success of plasma injection into the ovary

One of the main factors in the success of ovarian plasma treatment is to separate the plasma in a proper manner and inject it at the right time to ensure that the blood does not clot, and to avoid premature activation of platelets.

The place where the plasma injection takes place is very important as the stem cells are located in the ovarian cortex so they must be included during the plasma ovarian stimulation process. It is considered the first successful plasma injection case conducted in the United States of America and achieved good results. Over time, the technique has become much more successful in our time, and blood plasma is injected in Egypt now with great success (18). We also mentioned that the first case of prp plasma injection was not successful enough, and this technique depends on the injection of RP into the ovary, and the anesthesia is in the hospital, during which the concentrated platelet-rich plasma is injected.

The process of injecting plasma into the ovary (prp), that PRP injection is a procedure through which concentrated plasma is injected and doctors inject the plasma directly into the ovaries. One of the successful cases who tried injecting plasma into the ovaries says that she was suffering from severe ovulation weakness at the age of forty, and says my experience with plasma injections into the ovaries was successful, thanks to God by Prof. Dr. Mohamed Abdel-Fattah (26).

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